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Implementing an e-learning mindset and e-learning skills among the teachers of a department

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ABSTRACT

New technologies appear increasingly in engineering education and create a pressure on the didactic design to keep up in adapting. Some teachers take the lead and try out various e-learning tools, but the main question is **how do we lift an entire department from traditional didactics to a mindset and skills for e-learning didactics?** This paper will explore: What are the main barriers and drivers for e-learning teaching development – and how should we consider this in an implementation plan?

Many teachers in our department are well on their way in using e-learning elements and we have interviewed a representative range of teachers individually to identify the most relevant questions, before we in fall 2019 interview all faculty members (70 persons) individually and all external professors (33 persons) through a questionnaire. We will move all courses to a new and better Learning Management System in September 2019 and during this establish a common approach and implementation, using change management inspired by the ADKAR-model. ADKAR stands for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability and Reinforcement.

The benefits of improved learning technologies are obvious, just as there are many examples of stand-alone first movers in engineering education. There are, however, fewer studies dealing with the individual teachers' motivations for developing e-learning skills. We will in the future focus on how to motivate and support the majority of teachers in getting on board with e-learning teaching.

1 INTRODUCTION

The department and the university have both had a 100 % increase of students in the last 10 years and expect this growth to continue, just as the university is in the process of renovating and modernising the classic teaching areas and the study areas and at the same time expands the laboratory facilities significantly. The teaching and learning is therefore in a transition process and will be re-evaluated and most likely transformed in order to create an improved learning environment. An essential part of this transition is to change the mindset of the teachers and to incorporate the e-learning mindset and skills in the transition, which we will look into in this paper.

Learning technologies are increasingly making their way into higher education with great potential for enhancing learning [1]. However, it is also clear to us, that an e-learning mindset and skills to develop interactive and engaging e-learning has not quite reached the majority of teachers at our department of civil engineering just as it is the case at other departments and other universities [1]. In order to gain the many benefits from learning technologies, such as more interactive and engaging learning experiences, flexibility, scalability, internationalization and individual learning paths, we need a more widespread use. That is why this paper will focus on how to motivate and support the majority of teachers at a department in developing e-learning skills, getting an e-learning mindset and use e-learning in their teaching.

This is a work-in-progress towards defining a strategy and a plan of action for the department regarding e-learning. A main challenge in this project is the area of tension between setting goals for teaching activities and the Danish academic tradition of the teacher's freedom of method.

This means in our opinion, that we can argue a lot in favour of using e-learning and list all the benefits without a significant shift in the use of e-learning. As we see it, we need to address the teachers' barriers and drivers (motivation factors and needs) in order to get more teachers engaged in using e-learning and benefiting from the new opportunities.

Our stepping-stone in the drive of this shift is the launch of a new Learning Management System (LMS) that is chosen for its ability to support online and blended learning and offers a range of built-in learning technologies. The benefits from this shift requires, however, a change of habit for the teachers and their acceptance of letting go of their normal control of a course. Many teachers have already without coordination started using e-learning tools and activities in their courses, but the department still lacks a complete strategy and action plan for this development.

We are not presenting a tried and tested implementation strategy, but we will present and discuss the approach that we will use to establish the strategy.

2 DEFINITIONS AND SCOPE

The term “implementing e-learning” is widely used, but with various perspectives. It requires a definition and clarification as to what constitutes e-learning in the specific case. Furthermore, an implementation strategy for e-learning also has a wide scope from everything regarding technical issues and choice of system and tools to pedagogical principles, organizational readiness and change management. In order to clarify the scope of this paper we shall begin with defining our perspective on e-learning implementation at our department.

2.1 How do we define e-learning?

The term “e-learning” can be used for anything from the use of a simple digital learning tool to describing courses and educations that are entirely online.

Dimensions of e-learning can also be used for clarifying purposes as described by Wagner et al. [2] who list the following dimensions: Synchronicity (asynchronous or synchronous), location (same place or distributed), independence (individual or collaborative) and mode (electronically only or blended). These illustrate the nuances and variety of what constitutes e-learning.

Like the term e-learning, blended learning is also used as a very broad term. It comprises both face-to-face learning and some form of online learning in a “blend” that should seek to take the advantages from both forms to get the optimal blend [3]. However, in practice the term is often used for courses that make use of online learning activities as “add-on” to traditional learning, while maintaining traditional lectures.

At the furthest end of the scale, a vision for e-learning implementation in higher education can be where “virtualisation and remote working technologies will enable us to study at any university in the world, from home” [4] – meaning that entire educations and degrees will be made accessible online in the form of e-learning. This vision requires a university wide transformation.

At the other end of the scale (in the broadest sense of the term) one could argue that using a webpage for course information and an LMS for access to course material, timetables and for sending announcements is e-learning. We do not consider this simple use of an LMS for administration as e-learning.

In our definition the use of integrated learning technology such as quizzes, peer review and videos will constitute e-learning.

In our current vision for our department, we will focus on promoting and enhancing the use of effective blended learning, as this would maximise the range of pedagogical options.

2.2 Changing the pedagogical principles

Implementing e-learning involves a change in the pedagogical mindset.

“One of the most crucial prerequisites for successful implementation of e-Learning is the need for careful consideration of the underlying pedagogy, or how learning takes place online. In practice, however, this is often the most neglected aspect in any effort to implement e-Learning.” [5]

In order to get the full advantage of e-learning through blended learning, the mindset and approach to teaching and learning would have to shift [6], where the teacher become a learning journey facilitator and let go of the traditional role as lecturer and thus let go of the control. This is a big change and requires both courage and a different set of skills than the classic teacher skills.

We expect this scenario to be the future for higher education learning, but it is not something that happens quickly or easily. Instead of setting the bar too high up front, a step-by-step approach seems prudent. For this reason, our first goal is getting all teachers accustomed to the basic use of our new LMS while inspiring them to experiment with the more advanced learning technologies that are accessible.

2.3 Implementing the change

There are many ways in which to address an e-learning strategy and implementation plan. The most important stakeholders are the teachers, the university and the students. From discussions with students, we know that they have a positive attitude towards increased use of learning technologies providing they are a real help in their learning, but we will not look further into the student perspective here, nor on the university situation. In this work-in-progress project, we will focus on the teachers as stakeholders, their motivations and barriers.

Our perspective on implementation will focus on the teachers' barriers and drivers for using e-learning. This will be the foundation of an implementation plan considering the principles of change management and exploring the various ways in which to support the teachers in getting the necessary knowledge, skills and experience in using e-learning.

3 METHODOLOGY

Based on a combination of literature review and our preliminary findings in the initial interviews with teachers at our department, we will identify the drivers and barriers for e-learning implementation, and propose a plan for developing e-learning skills and e-learning mindset among the teachers.

3.1 Reported experiences in other investigations

In a literature review on e-learning readiness factors in higher education [7] the authors conclude that skills and attitudes are the most significant factors in e-learning readiness. Another study [3] reported that the stated individual barriers in using e-learning are lack of time, lack of technological knowledge and skills, lack of incentives, lack of recognition for the work involved and organizational lack of policy, planning and support.

Lack of time and lack of knowledge, skills and experience are also mentioned as challenges in [8] & [2], where the last added that fear of student acceptance may be a barrier as well. Factors which are likely to increase motivation have been reported [4] as “the potential to reach new students and experiment with new technologies” whereas “inadequate technical support, time, and recognition of the work involved” is likely to decrease motivation.

The implementation process itself is well described by Blackburn [6], who points out the fact that “Change is often initiated by school administrators, not the teaching staff themselves.” This type of change often meets resistance because it entails a demand for acquiring new competences and spending time producing e-learning. Extra time that the teachers do not have. An imposed change in the fundamental ways of teaching is thus a barrier to be taken into account.

3.2 Initial interviews with teachers – preliminary findings

From our sample interviews with representative teachers – 6 teachers, one from each section at our department – we have gathered an overview of the drivers (*Table 1.*) and main barriers (*Table 2.*) that the teachers have for e-learning.

Table 1. Drivers

<p>Intrinsic motivation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A desire to create the best possible learning design – better quality in learning - A desire to develop and a curiosity and interest in new tools and technology - A desire to be more efficient in course administration by using automated processes
<p>Extrinsic motivation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solving a problem (burning platform) that requires a new course of action - Reward and recognition - Dedicated resources such as time, money or support - Command (being required to do so)

Table 2. Barriers

<p>Time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Finding the time – to learn how and execute (skills) - Lack of acknowledgement of time used - Time away from research
<p>Change of habit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hard to take the first step / getting started - Hard to do something different from what you are accustomed to do - Worry that it requires too much, need to rethink your entire course design
<p>Fear</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fear of not being the expert from lack of experience - Fear of letting go of control - Fear of trying something new and out of comfort zone

Negative attitude towards e-learning

- Disagreement with the pedagogical principles of e-learning
- An understanding of e-learning lacking the human interaction

Rules and practicalities

- Concern about living up to requirements (Current statement from our university is that the implementation of e-learning may not result in less face-to-face time between teacher and students).
- Not all educational content is suited for e-learning

We will investigate further into the drivers and barriers drivers for e-learning implementation by individual interviews with all our teaching staff this fall. The results will help determine which of the factors are dominant at our department and help in targeting the most important areas in the implementation plan. The interviews will also provide relevant successful use-cases of different learning technologies and pedagogical methods that can serve as inspiration and knowledge sharing within the department.

4 IMPLEMENTATION AND CHANGE MANAGEMENT

Any implementation process is a change – and in order to succeed with the implementation, it is necessary to recognize the need for change management and the focus on helping individuals move from one standpoint to another. The ADKAR change management model is a way of understanding the steps in a change process [9]. ADKAR stands for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability and Reinforcement. An important point is respecting the fact that the steps are addressed in this order. Moving forward too fast without people accepting the current step will not lead to success.

In our case with the launch of a new LMS, we started creating *awareness* well in advance. We introduced the notion of a new LMS arriving soon at department meetings. The message came from our head of department to underscore the benefits and necessity of the change and the alignment with department and university strategy. From there on, we recruited “pilot” teachers from each section being the first to try out the new system for a semester while getting their ongoing feedback about issues that needed to be solved for a smooth transition to this new system. The next step of creating *desire* for the change is perhaps too ambitious. We focused on getting acceptance of change and overcome resistance to engage. At this stage, the pilots already played an important role as the teaching staff was presented with respected peers who had made the change to the new LMS and shared their honest opinion and experience of the required effort, benefits and necessary change of habits. At a department workshop for teachers, we combined *knowledge* and *ability* by presenting the basic guide to getting started with the new LMS and engaging the teachers in using the system right away and migrate their courses to the new platform.

Getting the teachers to practice their ability to use the new LMS will be our focus in the coming period combined with providing just-in-time knowledge, best practice examples and individual support. As more teachers become accustomed to the basic features, we will present them with the possibilities of the more advanced features. We also need to consider how to provide *reinforcement* to sustain the change and the continuous progress. How can we provide acknowledgment for teachers well on the way?

This implantation plan currently only focuses on implementing the new LMS. We wish to expand the scope to the broader sense of e-learning implementation.

Our plan is supported by Blackburn [6] in his best practice advice for successful implementation, which furthermore includes providing funding and support to teaching staff that are re-engineering their course designs, creating a Community of Practice (CoP), recognize and reward teaching staff who reuse open learning materials. Finally, to accept resistance as part of the process and be prepared to deal with it.

5 DISCUSSION

We believe that a successful implementation of e-learning will require an effort on many different levels and that we must allocate resources to support the process if we wish to increase the degree of success. Now that we have begun the process, our focus point will be on

- Offering just-in-time-support to teachers as well as reaching out and follow up on teachers getting started.
- Expanding on the help resources and guides for learning technologies and pedagogical principles for e-learning.
- Interviewing the teachers to get information regarding their experience with e-learning that can be used as showcases in knowledge sharing.
- Arranging short workshops that will dive further into specific advanced functions in the LMS and relevant e-learning tools.
- Cultivating communities of practice for e-learning at our department over time. This has begun with arranging network meetings for the “pilots” that were the first to use the new LMS.

We will during the process look further into approaches, which further support the drivers and reduce the barriers. The questions are, however, which initiatives beyond what we have already stated should be considered? What other possibilities might there be for giving incentives for using e-learning? Should we consider a type of reward as motivation?

“Extrinsic rewards can be used to motivate people to acquire new skills or knowledge. Once these early skills have been learned, people may then become more intrinsically motivated to pursue the activity.” [10]

It is a question of how such acknowledgement and rewards can be used best in an academic community.

6 FUTURE WORK

This paper represent our work-in-progress towards an e-learning strategy and plan of action. We have focused on the more practical side of an implementation plan for our new LMS, which in time should lead to more use of e-learning.

In a larger perspective, we are interested in the strategic framework for our department in regards to e-learning. The next step will be to define the criteria for success and how we determine progress. This raises the questions: What are the ways to do this – both in quantity and quality? Do we measure number of courses on the new platform? Number of courses using advanced features, such as group enrolment, peer review, videos, quizzes? Number of courses using Flipped Classroom? Number of entirely online courses? Furthermore, what is the best way to measure effect on learning outcome?

We can measure the effect of the new use of e-learning by comparing: Grades, number of students completing the courses, number of students dropping out, student satisfaction with the courses. Will that be sufficient?

Other relevant questions that we have encountered in this process are: What are the basics in pedagogical principles and didactics for e-learning? What does a teacher need to learn in order to be able to develop online or blended learning courses? Alternatively, from another perspective one could raise the question: Should all higher education teachers in time be able to produce e-learning – or would it be more effective to flip it – where the course design, structure and production is determined by an e-learning team and the teacher provides the contents?

REFERENCES

- [1] Lonn, S. & Teasley, S.D. (2009). Saving time or innovating practice: Investigating perceptions and uses of Learning Management Systems. *Computers & Education*, 53, pp 689-694.
- [2] Wagner, N., Hassanein, K. & Head, M. (2008). Who is responsible for E-Learning Success in Higher Education? A Stakeholder' Analysis. *Educational Technology & Society*, 11 (3), pp 26-36.
- [3] Ma, J. (2010). Implementing E-learning in Traditional Universities: Drivers and Barriers? Jönköping International Business School, Jönköping University. Retrieved from <http://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:323234/FULLTEXT01.pdf> Retrieved 25.04.2019.
- [4] MacKeogh, K. & Fox, S. (2008). Strategies for embedding e-learning in traditional universities: drivers and barriers. Roy Williams (ed) 7th European Conference on e-learning. Academic Publishing Ltd. Vol 2, pp 135-41.

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- [5] Govindasamy, T. (2002). Successful implementation of e-Learning – Pedagogical considerations. *Internet and Higher Education* 4, pp 287-299.
- [6] Blackburn, G. (2017). Successful eLearning Implementation: Best Practices. <https://elearningindustry.com/successful-elearning-implementation-best-practices> Retrieved 25.04.2019.
- [7] Hetty Rohayani.AH, Kurniabudi & Sharipuddin (2015). A Literature Review: Readiness Factors to measuring e-Learning Readiness in Higher Education. *Procedia Computer Science* 59, pp 230-234.
- [8] Bagiati, A. (2014). Developing an online Course: Challenges and Enablers. SEFI 42nd Annual Conference, Birmingham, UK.
- [9] The Prosci ADKAR model for change management, <https://www.prosci.com/adkar/adkar-model> Retrieved 25.04.2019.
- [10] Cherry, K. (2018). Extrinsic vs. Intrinsic Motivation: What's the Difference? Retrieved from <https://www.verywellmind.com/differences-between-extrinsic-and-intrinsic-motivation-2795384> Retrieved 25.04.2019